

Supplementary File S1b - Expanded EFA Fit Indices for WHOQOL-BREF

tem	Description (short label)	Domain				Extraction
		Psychological	Environment	Physical Health	Social Relationships	
1	Are you satisfied with your life?					
2	Are you satisfied with your health?	Not included				
3	To what extent do you feel that (physical) pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?			0.930		0.801
4	How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?			0.869		0.737
5	How much do you enjoy life?	0.857				0.802
6	To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?	0.742				0.769
7	How well are you able to concentrate?	0.530		0.362		0.511
8	How safe do you feel in your daily life?		0.684			0.613
9	How healthy is your physical environment?		0.775			0.513
10	Do you have enough energy for everyday life?			0.756		0.680
11	Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?	0.946				0.793
12	Have you enough money to meet your needs?		0.638			0.671
13	How available is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?		0.747			0.657
14	To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?		0.662			0.490
15	How well are you able to get around?			0.739		0.469
16	How satisfied are you with your sleep?			0.516		0.584
17	How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?	0.366		0.457		0.671
18	How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?			0.505		0.385
19	How satisfied are you with yourself?	0.855				0.804
20	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?				0.910	0.804
22	How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?				0.928	0.810
23	How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?		0.623		0.440	0.567
24	How satisfied are you with your access to health services?		0.618			0.557
25	How satisfied are you with your transport?		0.690			0.558
26	How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, and depression?	0.936				0.787

Note: Only factor loadings ≥ 0.30 are shown. Extraction method: principal component analysis. Rotation: Promotion with Kaiser

normalization.